

Again owing to micelle formation, the observed activity of the Cl^- ions may not vary proportionally with the concentration of the micelles. This fact will be evident from the following consideration.

The data in Table I shown that the difference of potential between the cells in experiment (2) and (4) is 40.1 mv. If $(a)_4$ and $(a)_2$ represent the activities of the Cl^- ions in the colloidal solutions in vessel II corresponding to the experiment (4) and (2) respectively then the following relation should hold good

$$0.059 \log \frac{(a)_4}{(a)_2} = 0.0401 \text{ volt}$$

It, therefore, follows that $(a)_4/(a)_2 = 4.79$ nearly. The corresponding increase in the ratio of micelle concentration according to Murray and Hartley⁷ and also Ghosh⁸ is equal to $\frac{(0.064-0.0008)}{(0.008-0.0008)}$ or 8.8 times approximately. Thus an increase of 8.8 times in the ratio of micelle concentration produces an observed increase of 4.79 times only in the ratio of the activities of the Cl^- ions. The experimental results, therefore, lead to the conclusion that the sol concentration effect is quite considerable even when the use of a salt bridge is avoided and the potential at the liquid/liquid junction is kept very low (if not eliminated altogether).

Further work on this line is in progress.

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12-Molybdophosphates of Biguanides and Related Compounds

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THISTLETHWAITE *et al.*¹⁻⁵ have prepared a number of 12-molybdophosphates of group I, group IIA, group IIB metals, ammonium and different metals of first transition series. Broadbank *et al.*⁶ have reported the synthesis of 12-molybdophosphates of alkali metals, ammonium and different organic amines. Biguanides and guanylureas are considered as strong amines and form stable normal and acid salts. 12-Molybdophosphates of Biguanides and guanylureas have been prepared by direct reaction between 12-molybdophosphoric acid and the appropriate amine carbonates and the reactions were carried out over water bath until all the effervescence ceases. The salts were isolated from the concentrated mother liquor.

Analysis: Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro Duma's method. Phosphorous was estimated acimetrically and hydron content was determined from the pH measurement of a definite amount of the salt. Thermal behaviours of biguanidium-12-molybdophosphate were studied by heating weighed quantity of salts between 50°-500° temperature in a muffle furnace and each time noting the weight losses.

All the salts are water soluble compounds and the dry crystalline salts contains large number of water of crystallization. Complete loss of water of crystallization takes occurred at about 250° and above 450° the compounds were found to decompose completely. From the Table 2 the apparent basicity of the 12-molybdophoric acid seen to be above 3. This results support the works of Thistlethwaite and others. According to Ripon¹ 12-molybdophosphoric acid has three strong hydrogens and further hydrogen of the hydrated complex can ionize under certain conditions. The additional H^+ seems to stabilize biguanide salts because at pH 7, $\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ ion becomes unstable and degraded to simpler anions.

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TABLE I

Compound	% of N	% of P	% of Mo	N : P	Water of crystallisation per $\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ ion
1. Biguanidium 12-molybdophosphate	4.42	1.42	52.7	6.90 : 1	14.12
2. Guanylurea 12-Molybdophosphate	3.40	1.35	51.1	5.58 : 1	15.70
3. Ethylbiguanidium 12-Molybdophosphate	4.49	1.39	—	7.14 : 1	12.11
4. Phenylbiguanidium 12-Molybdophosphate	4.54	1.29	—	7.79 : 1	16.09
5. Guanylurea-O-Ethylether 12-Molybdophosphate	3.34	1.39	—	7.39 : 1	12.87

TABLE 2

Compound	pH	C _H	Equivalent free H per mole of PMO ₁₂ O ₄₀	Equivalent of amine cation per mole of PMO ₁₂ O ₄₀	Apparent basicity of 12-Molybdo- phosphoric acid
1. Biguanidium 12-Molybdophosphate	2.23	0.005888	1.34	2.76	4.10
2. Guanylurea 12-Molybdophosphate	2.02	0.009550	1.27	2.79	4.06
3. Ethyl biguanidium 12-Molybdophosphate	2.13	0.007413	1.10	2.856	3.956
4. Phenylbiguanidium 12-Molybdophosphate	2.06	0.008710	1.127	3.116	4.243
5. Guanylurea-O-ethylether 12-Molybdophosphate	2.18	0.006607	1.37	2.664	4.034

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Proton-ligand Stability Constants of Substituted Ortho-Hydroxy Butyrophenones and their Oximes

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THE knowledge of proton-ligand stability constants is a prerequisite for the calculation of metal-ligand stability constants. Again, these values are required to be determined accurately because the values of pL are dependent on them. The present work was undertaken because of our interest in exploring the equilibria which exist when metal ions interact with these ligands.

Experimental, Results and Discussion

The 3-methyl (3MeOHB), 4-methyl (4MeOHB) and 5-methyl (5MeOHB) derivatives of 2-hydroxy butyrophenone (OHB) and their oximes were prepared as described earlier^{1,2}.

An inert atmosphere was maintained by bubbling nitrogen gas through the solution. Potassium nitrate (B.D.H.) was used to keep the ionic strength constant. Standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) solution was prepared according to the method of Allen and Low³. Dioxane was purified by the method of Vogel⁴ and was freshly distilled before use. The pH measurements, the experimental technique and the methods of calculations of \bar{n}_H and 2K_H were the same as described earlier^{5,6}.

Although the oximes contain two dissociable protons, only one proton was observed to dissociate from any of the oximes. Thus all the oximes under study were considered as monobasic acids. The practical values of proton-ligand stability constants were calculated as described earlier⁵. The average values of practical constants obtained are summarized in Table 1. Verification of the results by duplicate experiments gave the log 2K_H values agreeing within ± 0.05 log unit.

The data in Table 1 show that introduction of a methyl group in any of the positions 3, 4 and 5 of the benzene nucleus results in weakening of the acid strength of OHB. This is consistent with electron releasing character of the methyl group.

The relative order of acid weakening effect obtained is 3Me \gg 4Me > 5Me. The relatively small difference in the pK values of 5MeOHB and 4MeOHB, which is almost within the estimated range of experimental error, raises some doubt as to the significance that could be attached to it. Nevertheless, the data do reflect the trend in the acid strength of these ketones.

3MeOHB is a considerably weaker acid than OHB. This may be attributed to the orthoposition of the methyl group in 3MeOHB. This will exert greater inductive effect on electron density at phenolic oxygen, force the -OH group to form hydrogen bond with keto group in all the molecules and increase hydrogen bond strength over that in OHB, and also decrease the stability of the anion of the acid due to the crowding by methyl group around the charge centre (O⁻) that would restrict the solvent molecules in their approach and interaction.

In 4MeOHB there is no forced orientation of -OH group which strengthens the hydrogen bond. However, inductive effect of the meta methyl group is expected to be smaller in view of enlarged distance